

THE ROLE OF THE WORK "TARIXI FARG'ONA" (HISTORY OF FERGANA) WRITTEN BY ISHAQ KHAN IBRAT IN RESEARCHING THE ETHNIC SITUATION OF THE PEOPLE OF FERGANA VALLEY

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ABSTRACT

This article is written about the work "History of Fergana" written by Ibrat son of Is'haq Khan Junaidullahkhoja and the ethnographic information in it. The article "History of Ferghana" provides important information about the ethnic situation of the population of the Ferghana Valley at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the ethnopolitical and migration processes that took place in the valley, and the ethnotoponomics of the valley cities.

KEYWORDS: *Kokan Khanate, Ethnic Composition, Kipchaks, Yuuzs, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs, Tajiks, Ethnopolitical Processes, Migration Processes, Etnotoponomics.*

INTRODUCTION

In the works of local historians who lived in the period of the Kokan Khanate and later, information reflecting the ethnic situation in the Ferghana Valley is relatively rare. After all, the works of local historians of this period are mainly dedicated to showing the socio-political, cultural and economic life of the population of the Khanate, and the issue of ethnic and inter-ethnic relations is not well covered in them. This situation increases the importance of a wider scientific research of written sources recorded by local historians in the study of this issue. Because from them you can find information about the ethnic status of the peoples of the Fergana Valley, the economic and cultural types of the ethnic communities, as well as the ethnopolitical and migration processes that took place in the valley.

Relevance and Current Status of The Topic

One of such local written sources is the work "History of Fergana" written by Ibrat son of Ishaq Khan Junaidullahkhoja, a well-known representative of the Jadidism movement. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "Ibrat Domla's selfless services for the development of our country are a real example for all of us not only in his time, but also today."

Ishaqkhan Ibrat was born in 1862 in the town of Torakorgan near Namangan. His family goes back to the famous mystic Ahmed Yassavi. Ishaq Khan Tora's mother, Huribibi, played a big role in his literacy. Ishaq Khan Ibrat wrote about this: "In the past, I studied with three teachers in the neighborhood school for several years, and in the end I did not become literate, then I studied at the current girls' school in our house, under the care of my deceased parent" [2 - B.36]. Ishaq Khan Ibrat later studied at the Muhammad Siddiq Tunqator madrasa in Kokon [3 - B.9].

He visited many cities of Eastern and Western nations and studied the language, culture and customs of the local population. In one of the local press of that time, the following information was given about Ishak Khan Ibrat's knowledge of a number of languages, "... Fazili is a distinguished judge, he knows Turkish, Persian, Hindi, Russian, and is able to write letters in Russian, French, Armenian and other languages" [1] .

In addition, Ishaq Khan was well versed in the science of history. As a historian-scientist, Ishaq Khan Tora Ibrat took part in the scientific meeting dedicated to the history of the city of Akhsi, organized by the Russians in Tashkent in July 1913. His lecture will be published in the newspaper of the Turkestan region under the Russian title "Istoriya drevnego goroda Akhsi v Ferganskoy oblasti" according to the editorial rules of the newspaper. In this article, Ibrat thinks about the location of the city of Akhshi, the fact that it was once a flourishing city, when and for what reason it was destroyed, and what kind of villages were built in its place, based on historical-scientific works, factual materials, and archaeological finds [3 - B .59].

Conduct Research

Ishaq Khan Tora Ibrat's work "History of Ferghana" is dedicated to the history of Ferghana Valley. The work was written in 1916. At the same time, it is worth noting that the sources mention that this work was written in 1913 [3 - B.45]. This work was revised and published in 1925-1926 based on the requirements of the soviet ideology. It should also be mentioned that in the process of creating the work "History of Fergana" by Ishaq Khan Ibrat, who was well versed in Western languages, the famous Orientalist scientists V. V. Radlov, V. V. Barthold and V. P. He made good use of the works of Nalivkin and Herman Vambery and expressed his attitude to them [3 - B.48].

Analysis of the Obtained Results

If you read the book "History of Fergana" by Ishaq Khan Ibrat, you will know that it contains important information about the history of the Fergana Valley from ancient times to the conquest of the Kokan Khanate by the Russian Empire. The value of this work for us is that it also contains some ethnographic information. However, the author gave interesting information about the ethnic composition of the population of the Ferghana Valley at that time. For example, at the beginning of the 20th century, it was recorded that the majority of the population of the Fergana Valley consisted of Uzbeks, Sorts, Tajiks, Karakalpaks, Kipchaks, and nomadic Kyrgyz peoples from the mountain sides, and also that Jewish, Indian, Armenian, Persian, and Georgian peoples engaged in trade lived in the cities of the valley. Through the work, we can get important information about the ethno-political processes that took place in the Ferghana Valley at the end of the 19th century and the participation of different ethnic communities in them. It is also shown that Kipchak, Kyrgyz, Tajik, Kazakh, Yuz and other ethnic communities actively participated in the ethno-political processes of the Kokan Khanate.

It is known that the Kipchaks began to play an important role in the ethno-political life of the Kokan Khanate from the middle of the 19th century. This happened in connection with the appointment of Muslim Qul, the leader of the Qipchak tribe, who helped Koqan Khan Sheralikhan to come to the throne, as the thousand head. "During the time of Sherali Khan, the government was in the hands of Kyrgyz Kipchak" [4-B.301]. Later, during the reign of Khudoyar Khan, Musulmonqul had a great position and was appointed to the position of

thousandbashi. In order to develop the agriculture of the population, he created the river "Chinabad" and built a madrasa in the city of Koqan under the name of the khan. During the Musulmonqul period, the Kipchaks were given many territories and privileges. Khan and his officials belonging to other ethnic groups did not like this situation. "Consequently, in order to get rid of these cruel oppressions, they started working against the Muslims" [4 - B.298]. Khudoyar Khan and his officials beat the commander of the thousand Musulmonqul in a place called Bilqillama and killed him and his people [4 - B.299]. During these ethno-political processes, many innocent Kipchaks also perish.

On the eve of the Russian invasion, at the end of the 19th century, Abdurahman Aftobachi, the son of Musulmonqul, played an important role in the political life of the Kokan Khanate. It can be seen that the Kipchaks were a great political power in the khanate from the middle of the 19th century to the end of the 19th century, that is, until the termination of the Kokan Khanate.

In addition to the Kipchaks, we can learn from the work that the Kyrgyz also played an important role in the ethno-political life of the Kokan Khanate. It is written about this in the work "History of Fergana" that the Kipchaks and the Kyrgyz contributed equally to Sherali Khan's accession to the throne [4 - B.298] and that they also played an important role in the political life of the khanate. It is recorded in the work that the two wives of Sheralikhan and the father-in-law of the Musulmonqul Qipchak, the governor of Ketmontepa, Irisqulibi, were Kyrgyz [4 - B.297].

In addition, in the work "History of Fergana" there is information that Khushvaqtbek, who worked as a koshbegi during the time of Muhammad Ali Khan, was from the yuz tribe [4 - B.296].

It is stated that when the Russian Empire invaded the territory of the Kokand Khanate, Amirlashkar Aliquli appointed a person named Davlat Tajik as the governor of the city of Turkestan. It can be seen from this that Tajiks also played an important role in the ethno-political life of the Kokan Khanate at the end of the 19th century.

In the work "History of Fergana" there is also information about the important role of Kazakhs in the political life of the Kokhan Khanate. The work contains important information about the meeting of Amirlashkar Aliquli in Shymkent and negotiations with the leader of the Kazakh tribes, Boyzaqbi, and the relations of the Kazakhs with the Russian Empire.

Ishaq Khan Tora Ibrat's "History of Fergana" contains important information about the migration processes in the Fergana Valley. The work describes the migration of a group of residents of the Ferghana Valley to Kashgar during the period of Koqan Khan Muhammad Ali Khan between 1829 and 1832. In particular, first Buzrukhortora, and in the following years, under the leadership of Jahangirxantora and Isobek mehtars, Kashgar people and together with them some Kokan residents moved to Kashgar. Later, they united and settled in a place called Gulbog, belonging to the territory of China [4 - B.296].

In the work, the ancient cities of the Ferghana Valley; Geographical and ethnographic information is given about the cities of Kokan, Andijan, Namangan, Toraqorgan. In particular, there is historical and ethnographic information about the emergence of the cities of Ko'kan, Andijan, Namangan, and their names [3 - B.57] In the work "History of Fergana" by Ishaq Khan Tora Ibrat, some city names are explained ethnotopically. For example, in this work, the

author puts forward an opinion about the name of the city of Andijan: "Andigon" means "Andes", "Anda" is a tribe of Turks and Uzbeks.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that Ishaq Khan Ibrat's "History of Fergana" is of special importance among the local sources that reflect the ethnic situation in the Fergana Valley in the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. Through this work, we can get important information about the ethnic status of the Fergana Valley population, the ethno-political and migration processes that took place in the valley, and the ethnotoponomics of the regions.

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